

ANALYSIS OF ONLINE TEACHING-LEARNING TOOLS FOR EXACT SCIENCES AND BASIC ENGINEERING CYCLE

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Summary

The use of technology in education is essential for improving knowledge, facilitating learning and increasing student interest. In addition to the applicability of active and teaching-learning methodologies, identifying educational strategies and deepening the content taught. This research aims to analyze online support platforms for teaching and learning for high school students in relation to the exact subjects studied and virtual teaching tools to complement the study of engineering university students. The methodology used is through basic, descriptive and bibliographical research. Data collection was carried out using scientific articles, academic journals, online platforms, social media and annals of scientific events, in order to verify which existing online platforms support the exact science content studied by teaching students. high school and engineering universities. This work is fundamental for high school and university engineering students, as it identifies online platforms as support for learning, in the search to deepen knowledge regarding the contents demanded by teachers in the classroom for both students, giving flexibility to studies so that learning becomes more attractive.

Keywords: Study Platforms; Engineering; High school; Undergraduates; Technology and Education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Analyzing the exact science subjects taught in high school, the need was felt to study teaching-learning methods so that students are not just tied to the few and reasonable contents offered in schools by teachers, which directly affects them when taking tests in the classroom, especially when the more complex subjects involved math and logical reasoning.

Furthermore, the difficulties faced by academics in the disciplines of the basic engineering cycle, due to the precariousness of quality teaching before entering university and the deficiencies in the basic subjects involving the four basic operations such as arithmetic, expressions, logical reasoning and equations. As a consequence, regular education students do not learn the minimum necessary to take the entrance exams in their respective areas and engineering graduates do not do well in the subjects in the basic cycle of the course in the initial periods.

According to Monte (2015), in relation to the Brazilian context regarding the teaching of mathematics for Regular Education students, it presents itself as one of the primary problems for the development of the teaching-learning process, of the Mathematics discipline for High School students, as it refers to the identification and qualification of the teacher to teach this subject. Added to this is the complexity of the content and being taught. Still for the author, it is noted that the teaching of Mathematics is fragmented in High School, as it is a subject with complex content when it involves first and second degree equations, trigonometry, linearity, the combination of letters and numbers, as they can be elements that contribute to student learning difficulties.

Data analyzed by the National Council for Higher Education (CNE, 2015), of the students who enter university, 49% drop out of undergraduate education in the areas of engineering in the first periods of college, due to the high complexity of the exact content and the low load knowledge of the subject covered in the classroom.

The way to develop teaching-learning strategies virtually to complement the studies of high school and university engineering students, so that they can study wherever they are and choose the best study time, is essential for connecting students and academics with knowledge that goes beyond the classroom and is a fundamental practice so that they can be inserted into the professional field during training, in addition to updating themselves through virtual tools.

This work aims to investigate the main online platforms to complement the studies of high school students through teaching-learning in a virtual style and study support for engineering students regarding the exact subjects taught during the first periods of the basic cycle. of engineering.

2. BIBLIOGRAPHIC REVIEW

2.1. Virtual study and learning

According to Pimentel (2006), the virtual environment is characterized as a space where synchronous and asynchronous activities can be carried out in order to advance students' teaching and learning. It is around this online learning environment that Distance Education takes place, as it still presents some tools that are available in the Online Learning Environments. Virtual Learning Tools (VLE) that are commonly used by teachers and students. In the view of Oliveira (2018), in the virtual space, the organization of courses based on the Distance Education format stands out, based on theories, content and methodologies, as well as recognizing the importance of teamwork to ensure your objectives educational. This type of teaching has encompassed multiple tasks and the support of a multidisciplinary team that brings information to students in an integrated and dynamic way is essential.

According to Masseto (2017), new techniques develop students' curiosity and encourage them to seek, on their own initiative, the information they need to solve problems or explain phenomena that are part of their professional life.

So, according to Riel (1996), it is through virtual teaching that the student will be able to leave the isolation environment and enrich their knowledge, asking questions, expressing opinions and diverse reading, that is, the student will create a new interactive pedagogical dynamic that makes it easier for you to learn more than what is taught in the classroom. As Pereira (2007) highlights, the advancement of technology has changed the way we teach and learn at an overwhelming pace, associated with the complexity of tasks that require information and technology, making the educational process also adapt to the current world.

3. METHODOLOGY

The present study is characterized as basic in nature, this research has as its main objective “the advancement of scientific knowledge, without any concern with the immediate applicability of the results to be collected” (APPOLINÁRIO, 2011). This basic research is essential for searching for information in different subareas of exact sciences, in order to expand the knowledge of high school and undergraduate students regarding virtual study tools.

As for the classification of the research, in relation to the approach, this is a descriptive research, which according to Selltiz et al. (1965), seeks to describe a phenomenon or situation in detail, especially what is occurring, allowing the characteristics of an individual, a situation, or a group to be accurately covered, as well as unraveling the relationship between events. This descriptive research is essential to detail the tools that are being researched and analyzed, in order to

characterize their applications in teaching-learning for regular education and university students.

The classification of research according to technical procedures is a bibliographical research, which for Fonseca (2002), this type of research involves theoretical references already analyzed and published, which allows the researcher to learn about the study addressed. The study was carried out by collecting data through scientific articles, academic journals, database of theses and dissertations, online platforms, websites, blogs and annals of scientific events, addressing the theme of online platforms for teaching-learning of students of high school and engineering students.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The analysis of virtual tools for the teaching-learning of high school students in exact sciences and engineering undergraduate subjects arose due to the difficulty of a portion of high school students not having enough knowledge to face tests in the classroom and even entrance exams for engineering courses and other exact science courses that required prior knowledge of the subjects covered in mathematics, physics, chemistry and science subjects. And because undergraduate students did not specifically find platforms that provided the necessary support for content that involved logical reasoning, equations and numerical expressions, as support for fixing the content taught in the basic engineering cycle.

Furthermore, due to the fact that a number of engineering academics do not have such an interest in subjects in the basic engineering cycle, taught in the first years of graduation, due to the gap in the basic exact subjects that they studied in regular education and that many students took with them of the academic institution and the lack of interest in taking face-to-face academic reinforcement classes due to the fact that they do not have time to take the course due to studying full-time or spending a lot of time involved in extracurricular activities. Scientific articles and a bank of theses and dissertations were used to better support the established contents. We researched the exact sciences and engineering platforms that are most used by high school students and engineering students, respectively.

It is important to emphasize that when researching through websites and virtual platforms, each content is treated in a particular way and contributes significantly to students. In this way, the websites and online platforms researched are essential to facilitate the understanding of students who are experiencing problems in fixing exact content, since the limitations of these subjects ended up leaving gaps in the study. Figure 1 below represents the “Smart Sparrow” platform, which is aimed at high school and higher education students and has the possibility of allowing

students to create an interactive and adaptive course according to their needs. It is a tool that facilitates the creation of impactful and impressive experiences serving as pedagogical support for high school students, as well as having materials according to the profile of each student and availability, an analysis panel and detailed reports, educational games to develop the student learning.

Figure 1 – Smart sparrow platform

Source: <https://www.smartsparrow.com/>

Figure 2 below shows the “Dream Box Learning” platform aimed at developing mathematics and reading, using gamification to personalize all decision-making, resolving issues, as well as maintaining student interactivity and answering questions as many as possible. exercises and tests.

Figure 2 – Dreambox learning platform

Source: <https://www.dreambox.com/>

Figure 3 is the “Knew ton” tool, a platform that offers personalized content for high school students. In addition to providing each student with personalized learning based on individual needs in the subjects of calculation, mathematics and statistics, chemistry and physics.

Figure 3 – Knewton online tool

Source: <https://www.knewton.com/>

Figure 4 below represents the online platform “Geekie Games”, a Brazilian adaptive teaching tool that offers personalized teaching through games to help students prepare for the ENEM (National High School Exam), as well as identifying difficulties of students through algorithms. It has video classes, exercises, and interactive games to improve the level of high school students when taking the ENEM test.

Figure 4 – Platform for enem geekie games

Source: <https://geekiegames.geekie.com.br/>

In addition, seven platforms were identified for teaching students to study online:

- a) Coursera: is a platform that has content focused on Marketing Analysis, Game Design, Data Analysis, Data Science, Cloud Computing, Big Data, Digital Marketing, Social Media and E-Commerce.
- b) edX: provides free content from leading universities, colleges and schools around the world, including MIT, Harvard, Stanford, University of California, etc. This platform has content focused on Digital Knowledge and Engagement, Marketing, Project

Management, Artificial Intelligence, Data Analysis and Visualization, Accounting for Decision Making.

- c) Udacity: this has courses with an emphasis on the skills desired by technology companies, as well as autonomous car engineering and Artificial Intelligence;
- d) Udemy: includes subjects focused on design, marketing, personal development, engineering, among others.
- e) NovoEd: free and participants learn by collaborating on projects, sharing feedback and applying new skills directly in the workplace.
- f) Khan Academy: fundamental for online learning and offering topics for subjects from algebra, geometry, to preparation for proficiency tests, finance, economics, programming, chemistry, engineering and calculations and.
- g) Big Data University: covers subjects focused on data science, regression analysis, text analysis, data visualization and predictive modeling. It also deals with subjects about statistics, modeling, operating systems and decision making.

There are also some fundamental applications for strengthening learning in high school studies:

- i. Unit converter: is a converter that allows the transformation of common units, engineering, fluids, electricity, computing, light, time, magnetism, radiation, medical units and heat, without the need to use the internet.
- ii. Photomath: in this application it is possible to carry out mathematical calculations in a practical way, just taking a photo of the equation and the result appears on the device screen.
- iii. Geogebra: is a dynamic mathematics app that combines geometry and algebra concepts. This is used for teaching geometry, algebra, spreadsheets, graphs, statistics and calculation.
- iv. Chemistry: it is an app that brings together all chemistry content and it is possible to calculate reactions, show the periodic table, molar mass and study schemes on electronegativity of elements, molar weight of organic substances, reactivity series and acid resistance graph.
- v. Virtual platforms and engineering applications: fourteen online platforms focused on engineering and exact science content were identified. In this way, the majority are available to all audiences, namely: Coursera (created in Silicon Valley), edX (offers quality courses from the most reputable universities in the world), Udacity, Udemy, NovoEd, Khan Academy, Canvas Network, How U Hack Design, Skillcrush, Big Data University, Codecademy,

University of the People and Open UW. Furthermore, ten top websites for engineering students were identified.

Figure 5 below represents the “Eng-Tips.com” platform, which is essential for viewing debates and topics focused on various areas of engineering, such as Aeronautical and Space Engineering, Automotive, Chemical, Civil and Environmental, Computing, Electrical and Electronic, Geotechnical, Industrial and Manufacturing, Maritime and Oceanic, Materials, Mechanical, Structural, Oil and Gas, as well as answering student questions and creating online conversation forums. Within the platform there are debate rooms for students who study engineering and for professionals trained in engineering, as well as dealing with engineering codes, standards and certifications, the impact of the industry on professional training, project and configuration management, trends and strategies for each area of engineering.

Figure 5 – Eng tips platform

Source: <https://www.eng-tips.com/>

Figure 6 below is the “LearnChemE.com” platform, through which the student learns about chemical engineering through simulations and with the help of instructors available on the platform. On the platform you can observe the main topics such as catalysis, general chemistry, Computer Engineering and Mathematics, fluid mechanics, heat transfer, kinetics and reactor design, material and energy balances, physical chemistry, process control and design, separation and mass transfer, statistics, thermodynamics, as well as quizzes and exam reviews to improve the subjects studied. Within the platform it is possible to carry out interactive simulations of chemical and physical processes and have help from instructors.

Figure 6 - Learn cheme platform

Source: <https://learncheme.com/>

Figure 7 below represents the “Engineering Tool box” platform, where you can find important tools for carrying out calculations and exercises developed in engineering, and studying theoretical concepts to support tasks, free tools and information for engineering and design of technical applications. Within the platform there are several measurement unit conversion calculators to help students.

Figure 7 - Engineering tool box

Source: <https://www.engineeringtoolbox.com>

Figure 8 below is the “All About Circuits” tool, which is essential for complementing electrical engineering studies, as it facilitates students' understanding of subjects aimed at better understanding electrical circuits.

Figure 8 – All about circuits tool

Source: <https://www.allaboutcircuits.com>

Figure 9 below represents the “Aero Students” platform, this is a website for aeronautical engineering, with conceptual applications and the interactivity that this engineering offers. Being a platform that offers subjects on Engineering Design, Exploration of Aerospace Engineering, Introduction to Aerospace I and Statistics for the first period; for the second period the subjects are Aerospace Materials, Calculus I, Dynamics and Introduction to Aerospace II; for the third period there are the subjects Aerospace Design and Systems Engineering I, Calculus II, Design and Construction, Mechanics of Materials and Thermodynamics and for the fourth period, Linear Algebra and Waves and Electromagnetism.

Figure 9 – Aero students

Source: <https://aerostudents.com>

Figure 10 below is the virtual platform “Circuit Lab”, which represents everything about electronic engineering, applying concepts and teaching through interactive classes. Furthermore, the student has access to questions and answers, examples of practical applications and editing of electrical circuits.

Figure 10 – Circuit lab platform

Source: <https://www.circuitlab.com>

Below are other platforms that support engineering students, they are:

- a) Khan Academy: tool that seeks to improve skills and allows users to download videos and view them without needing an internet connection, helping students who do not have constant access to the internet.
- b) Engineering Institute: is a website that provides information for engineering students, as students have the possibility of accessing videos, the main news in the area in which they work, news and checking the date of seminars and conferences, as well as networking and meet other professionals
- c) Engineering Blog: the platform contains topics about engineering, technology, entrepreneurship, courses, the job market and open vacancies.
- d) Wolfram Alpha: shares in detail how to solve math equations, data analysis, computer science tips and technology.
- e) The Engineering Toolbox: provides different tools for exact science students, where students can find tables, articles and tools.

As a complement to the activities studied during graduation, there are other platforms below that serve as support for engineering students and recent graduates. Virtual applications and tools are fundamental to dynamism, productivity and assertiveness in the routine of future and professional engineers.

- a) A360: consists of a mobile version of AutoCad 360, being an essential tool for preparing technical drawing parts in two dimensions and creating three-dimensional models. Created and edited drawings can be viewed in more than 50 different file formats, compatible with BIM. It is worth noting that it has cloud storage and access to data without needing a connection.
- b) PlanGrid: is an application for engineering students and professionals to make appointments, photos, to-do lists and daily reports together with the team. This app has more than 50 saved plans, and can be used for construction projects;

- c) Construct app: it is a project management platform, as it allows you to monitor activities, manage the team and make possible decisions. In addition to being widely used by MRV.
- d) Engineering Unit Converter: is a robust and easy-to-use unit converter. It is an essential app for engineering and does not require an internet connection to work;
- e) Ms Calc: is widely used to carry out structural calculations and complies with NBR 6118, carries out sizing of civil structures and generates calculation memory reports in PDF;
- f) My Scrib Calculator: is a calculator that performs calculations from the simple to the most complex in real conditions, as if it had been done by hand naturally;
- g) Wolfram Alpha: it is highly recommended for carrying out mathematical calculations, and this is one of the most sought after apps by engineering students and professionals. Using simple commands, it is possible to solve problems in algebra, trigonometry, number theory, logical functions, physics and chemistry problems;
- h) Frame Design: is suitable for students and professionals in civil, mechanical, architectural engineering and designers who wish to create 2D structural drawings based on the finite element method;
- i) Phy: a tool that calculates physical problems with complex equations;
- j) Graphing Calculator: a tool for creating graphs in a scientific and simplified way.

5. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

All articles read for theoretical basis and the search for websites and media in the area of exact sciences were essential to outline the functionality of teaching-learning tools according to the profile of high school students who have some learning difficulties in relation to exact disciplines, as well as bringing tools that serve as support to engineering university students, as a complement to their studies of disciplines in the basic engineering cycle.

The internet has greatly improved the ability of students and university students to access knowledge without leaving home, as there are many tools that help students on their study journeys. It is important to highlight that in view of the readings carried out, it was observed that digital tools are increasingly contributing to the educational field in order to improve the teaching-learning of high school and undergraduate students. And making use of digital tools in the student's educational process is a way to achieve results and improve understanding of activities in a dynamic and interactive way.

Technological tools make learning fun, allowing students to interact with technology, gradually getting involved and allowing activities and subjects to become increasingly attractive, so that students can discover much further and can easily fix the content contained on the platforms. In view of the facts mentioned, numerous platforms, websites and software were collected that help high school and university students to train themselves, in most cases free of charge with exact science content, providing students with flexibility with the platforms in an interactive, assertive way. and flexible.

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